

ENZYMES ACTIVITIES OF PRE-GELATINIZED STARCH ADJUNCTS AND MALTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (50, 60, 70, AND 80 °C)

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ABSTRACT: Studies were carried out on the enzyme activities of pre-gelatinized starch adjunct and malts at different temperatures. The sorghum (red variety) was purchased, sorted, analysed (grain analysis), malted, analysed again (malt analysis), and milled. A total of 10g of the unmalted sorghum flour (adjunct) were weighed into 4 different 500ml conical flasks, distilled water (360ml) was added to the flasks and the mixtures were pre-gelatinized at different temperatures viz: 50, 60, 70 and 80°C after which 40g of malted sorghum grist were added to each conical flask with 1ml of exogenous enzymes (thermamyl, fungamyl, neutrase and amyloglucosidase). The samples were properly shaken before the infusion mashing technique was used to obtain worts of various concentrations. After mashing, the resulting worts were analysed, followed by worts boiling with hops for 1h 30mins. The boiled worts were cooled with subsequent pitching of yeast strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, before primary fermentation, which lasted 7 days, and secondary fermentation for another 14 days. The results of wort analysis showed original gravity ranging from 1030-1036 °p, sugar level (7.55-9.02) °Brix, pH (5.49-5.62), and viscosity (1.04-1.05)CP at room temperature. The beer analysis showed a specific gravity range of (1001-1002) °p, sugar level (0.26-0.52) °Brix, pH (3.80-3.89), % alcohol (3.6-4.5)%v/v at the temperature of 24°C. The results from sensory evaluation showed no significant differences among the samples based on the parameters tested at the $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance. The study concluded that, with proper processing and enzyme supplementation, sorghum can be effectively used as a malt or adjunct in beer production, offering a cost-effective and locally available alternative to barley in African brewing industries. Pre-gelatinization at 70°C according to this study yielded the best result and, as such, is the most suitable temperature for the gelatinization of sorghum starch.

Keywords: Enzymes Activities, Pre-Gelatinized Starch Adjuncts, Malts, Different Temperatures

INTRODUCTION

In the modern-day, large-scale commercial brewing sector uses several cereals are used as sources of starch to be hydrolyzed to fermentable sugars, namely maltose, maltotriose, and glucose (Han *et al.*, 2016). These cereals would be malted barley, wheat, sorghum, and an adjunct such as unmalted cereals, cassava, and potatoes (Ulfa *et al.*, 2021). Although some brewers may use a liquid sugar adjunct such as sucrose. Conversely, the craft, or small-scale brewing sector, often uses only malt barley as the sole source of starch to be hydrolysed into the fermentable sugars (Callejo *et al.*, 2020). Malted barley is usually the primary source of starch; specialty beers, such as wheat beers, also use malted wheat with malted barley, and traditional beers in African countries sometimes use sorghum (Elgorashi *et al.*,

2016). Most recently, raw cereals have been used with the addition of endogenous enzymes to produce the fermentable sugars required for fermentation (Goode *et al.*, 2005).

Regardless of the raw materials, brewers focus on fermentation efficiency due to its contribution to flavour and the amount of ethanol produced (Balcerek *et al.*, 2016). A substantial contribution to the fermentation process is the fermentable sugars produced from the hydrolysis of starch by enzyme action during the mashing stage (Ai *et al.*, 2013). Starch is the most abundant component in cereals, with two different polymers making up the total starch content.

Brewers are searching for various and unique attributes other than those already found in conventional commercial beers. The addition of adjuncts and other substances in brewing offered distinct flavor or biological activity and enriched the diversity of beers (Kawa-Rygielska *et al.*, 2019)

Sorghum was the most common adjunct in Africa, and the high starch content and low fat content made it appropriate for malting and beer brewing (Bogdan and Kordialik-Bogacka, 2017). The utilization of sorghum in brewing gave the extra advantage of reducing the levels of haze proteins and improving the clarity of the beer (Habschied *et al.*, 2020). As a low-priced starchy material, deep processing of sorghum is now emerging as the way to bring out added value, such as bioethanol fuel or alcoholic beverages.

Starch granules with different gelatinization characteristics exhibited variant enzymatic hydrolysis properties (De Schepper *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, the synergistic relationship between starch gelatinization and starch hydrolysis facilitated the mashing (Langenaeken *et al.*, 2019; Yu *et al.*, 2018). Structure formation in materials is affected by the ingredient properties and processing conditions (Ulfa *et al.*, 2019).

The efficiency of starch conversion in brewing and related industries depends largely on enzymatic activity, which is influenced by temperature. While malted grains provide natural enzymes, pre-gelatinized starch adjuncts lack sufficient enzymatic content and require supplementation. However, the specific temperature ranges that optimize enzyme activity in both malt and adjuncts remain unclear. This study seeks to address this gap by evaluating and comparing the enzymatic activities of these materials at different temperatures to improve process efficiency and product quality.

This study was aimed at investigating the enzymatic activities of pre-gelatinized starch adjunct and malts at different temperatures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sources of Materials

The materials used were the four basic raw materials for beer production, which include: water, a local variety of red sorghum malt, unmalted red sorghum as an adjunct, hops, and yeast. The red sorghum was purchased from Eke-Agbani in Nkanu-West local government of Enugu state. The hops, yeast, chemicals, and reagents used were supplied by the Department of Microbiology, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, ESUT.

Analytical Methods

The methods of analysis employed in the evaluation of grains, malt, wort, and beer were based on the recommended methods of analysis of the Institute of Brewing (IOB), American Society of Brewing

Chemists (ASBC), and Laboratory Methods in Malting. The raw red sorghum grains were analysed for their germinative energy, germinative capacity, moisture content, and thousand corn weight before malting (floor malting technique) was done.

The red sorghum malts were milled using a milling machine to obtain coarse grits used for mashing. Before mashing, the cold-water extract, hot-water extract, and diastatic power of the red sorghum malts were determined.

Pre-gelatinization

A total of 10g of the unmalted red sorghum flour (adjunct) was weighed into 4 different 500ml conical flasks and pre-gelatinized at different temperatures. The samples were labelled A (gelatinized at 50°C), B (gelatinized at 60°C), C (gelatinized at 70°C), and D (gelatinized at 80°C). Distilled water (360ml) was added to each of the conical flasks containing the adjunct. Pre-gelatinization was done by placing the conical flask in a water bath and raising the temperature. Each sample is removed when the desired temperature is reached and allowed to cool.

Mashing (Infusion Mashing Technique)

After pre-gelatinization, 40g of sorghum grist was added to each conical flask. About 1ml of exogenous enzymes: amyloglucosidase, fungamyl (β -amylase), thermamyl (α -amylase), and neutrase (proteinase) were added into each of the conical flasks containing the samples and shaken properly. The conical flasks were covered with aluminium foil and placed in a water bath to commence the mashing process. The temperature was raised to 35°C and maintained for 30 minutes. The temperature was raised again to 45°C and maintained for 30 minutes for Beta-glucanase activities. The temperature was raised again to 50°C and maintained for 30 minutes for proteolysis. The temperature was further raised to 63°C and maintained for 1 hour for Beta-amylase activities. Finally, the temperature was raised to 72°C and maintained for 30 minutes to allow for the activities of alpha-amylase. One (1) drop of iodine solution was added to check for saccharification and vigorously boiled for 10 minutes after a complete saccharification with yellow colouration as evidence. The essence of vigorous boiling for an extra 10 minutes is to mash off. The samples (mashes) were allowed to cool and filtered using filter cloth to obtain a clear solution known as worts.

Wort Analysis

At the end of the mashing, the resulting worts were analyzed for original gravity using a hydrometer, sugar content with a Brix refractometer, pH with a pH meter, flow rate through the titrimetric method, and other parameters determined, including viscosity, reducing sugars (maltose and glucose), and temperature using a thermometer.

Wort Boiling and Cooling

The worts were poured into 500ml conical flasks and arranged in a water bath, hops (pellets) were added and boiled for 1½ hrs, and afterwards cooled to room temperature.

Fermentation

Ten millilitres (10ml) of the reconstituted yeast inoculum (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) was added to the cooled and aerated worts (pitching), and the container was stocked with cotton wool to commence the primary fermentation, which took 7 days at 25 °C. Ultimately, the yeasts were skimmed off, and the

product was filtered to obtain green beer, which was then allowed to undergo secondary fermentation for 7 days at 10°C. After the secondary fermentation, the beer was filtered with filter paper to obtain a bright, clear beer.

Beer Analysis

At the end of primary and secondary fermentation, the beers were analyzed for specific gravity, pH, apparent fermentability, % alcohol, and temperature, following the methods of analysis of the Institute of Brewing.

Sensory Evaluation

An organoleptic test was carried out on the beer produced. A panel of 10 semi-trained assessors evaluated the beer samples and recorded their inferences and insights about the product. A 9-point hedonic scale was used, where 1 = Dislike extremely and 9 = Like extremely, for parameters (color, taste, mouth feel, and general acceptability) tested. The results of their judgment were subjected to statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

The color, taste, mouth feel, and general acceptability were tested, and information was collected using hedonic scales. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to evaluate the parameters. The results of the analysis were tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

RESULTS

According to Table 1, germinative energy (98%) and germinative capacity (96%) were both high, indicating that the sorghum grains were highly viable for malting. Moisture content (9.6%) is within the acceptable range for grain storage. The thousand-grain weight (24g) suggested a reasonable grain size and mass suitable for malting. Table 2 showed that hot water extract (295%/kg), indicating efficient solubilization of fermentable compounds. Cold water extract (24%) was moderate, showing fair solubility in cold conditions. Diastatic power (41.3°L) reflects moderate enzymatic activity, which might require supplementation with exogenous enzymes during mashing. Pre-gelatinization was done at four different temperatures for raw sorghum that is used as adjunct. The temperatures are 50, 60, 70, and 80°C. Worts were obtained from this pre-gelatinized adjunct, and the results of the analysis of the worts were recorded in Table 3. Original Gravity (O.G.) ranged from 1.030 to 1.036, indicating increasing sugar concentration with increasing adjunct levels. Sugar levels were highest in sample C (10% adjunct at 70°C), indicating optimum gelatinization and enzyme efficiency. Viscosity and Flow Rate and similar across samples; slight increases in viscosity are observed with higher adjunct levels. The results of the analysis of the beer samples after three days, primary and secondary fermentation were recorded in Tables 4, 5, and 6, respectively. All samples achieve high fermentability; however, Sample C maintains superiority in both alcohol content and overall sugar conversion. Table 7 contained the results from the sensory evaluation of the beer samples.

Table 1: Grain analysis

Parameters Tested	Red Sorghum
Germinative Energy (%)	98
Germinative Capacity (%)	96
Moisture content (%)	9.6
Thousand corn weight (G)	24

Table 2: Malt Analysis

Parameters tested	Red Sorghum Malt
Hot Water Extract (%/kg)	295
Cold Water Extract (%)	24
Diastatic power (°L)	41.3

Table 3: Wort Analysis

Samples	O.G (°p)	Sugar level (°Brix)	pH	Temp (°C)	Flow rate (Sec)	Viscosity (cp)	Reducing sugars (mg/l)	
							Glucose	Maltose
A	1.030	7.55	5.49	25	18.50	1.04	54.73	88.80
B	1.031	7.8	5.57	25	18.48	1.04	54.73	88.80
C	1.036	9.02	5.62	25	18.68	1.05	50.21	81.17
D	1.035	8.78	5.58	25	18.45	1.04	50.21	81.17

Key: Sample A gelatinized at 50°C, Sample B gelatinized at 60°, Sample C gelatinized at 70°C, and Sample D gelatinized at 80°C.

Table 4: Analysis after 3 days of fermentation

Samp les	Specific Gravity (°p)	Sugar level (°Brix)	Temp. (°C)	p H	% Alcoh ol	Apparent Fermentability (%)
A	1.007	1.8	25	4.0 2	2.97	76.7
B	1.006	1.54	25	4.0 1	3.23	80.7
C	1.006	1.54	25	4.2 0	3.87	83.3
D	1.008	2.05	25	4.1 9	3.48	77.1

Key: Sample A gelatinized at 50°C, Sample B gelatinized at 60°, Sample C gelatinized at 70°C, and Sample D gelatinized at 80°C.

Table 5: Analysis after Primary Fermentation

Samples	Specific Gravity (°ρ)	Sugar level (°Brix)	Temp. (°C)	pH	% Alcohol	Apparent Fermentability (%)
A	1.004	1.03	25	3.89	3.35	86.7
B	1.004	1.03	25	3.94	3.48	87.1
C	1.003	0.77	25	3.99	4.26	91.7
D	1.004	1.03	25	9.95	4.0	88.6

Key: Sample A gelatinized at 50 °C, Sample B gelatinized at 60°, Sample C gelatinized at 70°C, and Sample D gelatinized at 80°C.

Table 6: Analysis after Secondary Fermentation

Samp les	Specific Gravity (°ρ)	Sugar level (°Brix)	Temp (°C)	p H	% Alcoho l	Apparent Fermentability (%)
A	1.002	0.52	10	3.80	3.6	93.3
B	1.001	0.26	10	3.81	3.9	96.8
C	1.001	0.26	10	3.89	4.5	97.2
D	1.001	0.26	10	3.89	4.4	97.1

Key: Sample A gelatinized at 50 °C, Sample B gelatinized at 60°, Sample C gelatinized at 70°C, and Sample D gelatinized at 80°C.

Table 7: The Sensory Evaluation Table

	Colour	Taste	Mouth Feel	General Acceptability
F – Cal. Values	1.08	1.16	0.50	1.41
F – Tables values	2.866	2.866	2.866	2.866
LSD	0.522	0.522	0.379	0.524

Key: F-cal values = F calculated values

Discussion

This study evaluated the brewing potential of malted sorghum and pre-gelatinized sorghum adjuncts at varying temperatures, focusing on their effects on wort quality, fermentation efficiency, and final beer characteristics. Saccharification of cereal starches into fermentable sugars and unfermentable dextrins creates the basis of the wort, a sugary solution that is later fermented into beer. Saccharification during the mash is achieved by the activation of malt enzymes at the correct temperatures and moisture levels. To be susceptible to digestion by enzymes, the starches in malt or adjunct must first be gelatinized. This first cooking stage pasteurizes and also gelatinizes the sorghum adjunct, leaving virtually no ungelatinized starch in the mash. The first cooking and mashing steps

effectively increase the amount of beer that can be obtained from a given quantity of malt/adjunct (Zhang *et al.*, 2017).

The grain analysis (Table 1) revealed that the red sorghum used had high germinative energy (98%) and capacity (96%), indicating a viable raw material suitable for malting. The moisture content (9.6%) was within the safe storage range, and the thousand-grain weight (24g) confirmed acceptable grain size and mass.

In the malt analysis (Table 2), sorghum malt demonstrated a hot water extract of 295%/kg, indicating efficient solubilization of extractable compounds. The cold water extract (24%) and diastatic power (41.3°L) were moderately acceptable. However, this relatively low diastatic power suggests that the enzymatic activity of sorghum alone may be inadequate for complete starch conversion, necessitating the use of commercial enzymes during mashing.

The wort analysis (Table 3) showed that worts produced from sorghum adjuncts pre-gelatinized at different temperatures (50°C to 80°C) yielded varying sugar concentrations. Sample C, pre-gelatinized at 70°C, recorded the highest original gravity (1.0360ρ) and sugar level (9.02°Brix). This implies that 70°C was the optimal temperature for starch gelatinization, enabling maximum enzymatic hydrolysis and sugar release. The pH values of the worts (5.49–5.62) and their viscosity (1.04–1.05cp) fell within acceptable ranges for brewing, indicating good mashing performance and wort quality. Many other researchers (Adedokun and Itiola, 2010; Declan *et al.*, 2002; Elgorashi *et al.*, 2016; Schnitzenbaumer and Arendt, 2014) have gotten similar results.

Fermentation results (Tables 4 to 6) supported these observations. After 3 days of fermentation, Sample C showed the highest alcohol yield (3.87%) and apparent fermentability (83.3%). These values continued to rise through the primary and secondary fermentation, culminating in a final alcohol content of 4.5% and apparent fermentability of 97.2% for Sample C. This result showed that the value of alcohol produced is within an acceptable range for laboratory-scale brewing. Subsequently, the amount of sugar in the wort determines the amount of alcohol produced. This trend was directly related to its higher sugar content, affirming the principle that increased fermentable sugars lead to higher ethanol production. Sample D, with 20% adjunct, followed closely, suggesting that increased adjunct usage at suitable gelatinization conditions does not impair fermentative efficiency. This trend is similar to the results of Langenaeken *et al.* (2019), Lyumugabe *et al.* (2015), and Ogu *et al.* (2006).

Interestingly, all beer samples had a final pH range of 3.80–3.89, indicative of normal yeast metabolism and sufficient organic acid production. The low residual sugar content across all samples post-secondary fermentation (0.26–0.52°Brix) confirmed complete fermentation and minimal risk of post-packaging spoilage.

The sensory evaluation (Table 7) showed no significant differences in colour, taste, mouthfeel, and general acceptability among all samples ($p > 0.05$). This result is critical as it demonstrates that the inclusion of pre-gelatinized sorghum adjunct, even up to 20% did not negatively influence the sensory quality of the final beer. Therefore, sorghum adjuncts can be used in brewing without compromising consumer acceptability.

In summary, pre-gelatinization at 70°C provided optimal conditions for enzymatic hydrolysis of sorghum starch, leading to improved wort characteristics, enhanced fermentation performance, and acceptable beer sensory attributes. These findings are in agreement with previous studies (Adedokun and Itiola, 2010; Langenaeken *et al.*, 2019; Schnitzenbaumer and Arendt, 2014), which emphasized the importance of starch gelatinization in improving extract yield and enzyme activity in cereal-based brewing.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that sorghum is a suitable raw material for brewing, both as malt and as a pre-gelatinized adjunct. Pre-gelatinizing sorghum at 70°C was found to be the most effective, resulting in the highest extract yield and alcohol production. The use of exogenous enzymes significantly improved starch conversion. Importantly, the inclusion of sorghum adjuncts did not affect the sensory quality of the beer. Therefore, sorghum has great potential for use in commercial brewing, especially in regions where it is readily available.

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